

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE USE OF STEM TECHNOLOGY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDICATORS OF CREATIVITY

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Аннотация. Новые физические концепции, появившиеся с развитием общества, требуют постоянного совершенствования методики преподавания физики для того, чтобы войти в восприятие учащихся, творчески использовать их и добиться успеха в практической деятельности. Актуальной проблемой является разрешение противоречий между необходимостью использования STEM-технологий для развития креативности будущих специалистов-физиков и отсутствием исследований педагогических и психологических основ обучения созданию STEM продуктов с упором на творчество в образовательном процессе.

В данной статье определены концепция креативности будущих специалистов-физиков, методы диагностики креативности, компоненты и показатели креативности.

Ключевые слова: STEM-образование, креативность, будущие специалисты-физики, преподавание физики, компоненты и показатели.

Abstract. New physical concepts that have emerged with the development of society require constant improvement of physics teaching methods in order to enter into the perception of students, creatively use them and achieve success in practical activities. An urgent problem is the resolution of contradictions between the need to use STEM technologies to develop the creativity of future physics specialists and the lack of research on the pedagogical and psychological foundations of teaching STEM products with an emphasis on creativity in the educational process.

This article defines the concept of creativity of future physicists, methods for diagnosing creativity, components and indicators of creativity.

Keywords: STEM education, creativity, future physics specialists, teaching physics, components and indicators.

Annotatsiya. Jamiyat rivojlanishi bilan paydo bo'lgan yangi fizik tushunchalar o'quvchilarning idrokiga kirish, ulardan ijodiy foydalanish va amaliy faoliyatda muvaffaqiyatga erishish uchun fizika o'qitish usullarini doimiy ravishda takomillashtirishni talab qiladi. Bo'lajak fizika mutaxassislarining ijodkorligini rivojlantirish uchun STEM texnologiyalaridan foydalanish zarurati va o'quv jarayonida ijodkorlikka e'tibor qaratgan holda STEM mahsulotlarini o'qitishning pedagogik va psixologik asoslari bo'yicha tadqiqotlarning etishmasligi o'rtasidagi qarama-qarshiliklarni hal qilish dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada kelajakdagi fiziklarning ijodkorligi tushunchasi, ijodkorlikni diagnostika qilish usullari, ijodkorlik komponentlari va ko'rsatkichlari belgilanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: STEM ta'limi, ijodkorlik, bo'lajak fizika mutaxassislari, fizika o'qitish, komponentlar va ko'rsatkichlar.

Introduction. The training of future specialists who can meet the requirements of society is relevant. Therefore, to this day, new methods and methods of teaching, teaching aids, and new teaching technologies are being studied in higher educational institutions. In a changing society, achievements in the field of education are combined with the development of the direction of informatization.

Currently, the informatization of society is of particular importance in any field, including in the field of Education. During the period of rapid development of Information Technology, the effectiveness of the educational process of secondary educational institutions is directly related to the professional training of the future teacher. Therefore, it is important to inform the educational process in higher educational institutions that train future specialists.

In a changing society, STEM education occupies a special place in the formation of a creative person who has the ability to make decisions independently in various situations, is able to quickly find a way to solve problems, easily solve the difficulties encountered in meeting the requirements of a developed society [1].

The process of STEM education, its main directions, the development of the content, purpose, principles, pedagogical foundations of training future specialists in the context of the use of STEM technologies and a system of assessment incentives to improve the quality of education are developed by several foreign and domestic scientists Saputro, V. C. E., Wasis, & Prastowo, T. [2], Scalettar, B.A., & Abney, J. R. [3], Kazbekova G.N., Ismagulova J.S. [4], RamankulovSh., ChoruhA., Polatuly S. [5] and so on. However, the methodology of teaching individual disciplines through the use of STEM technologies in the training of future physics specialists does not fall into a single system, but is formed at the level of individual recommendations. One of these disciplines is physics.

Although many studies have highlighted the importance of STEM education in teaching physics, it has been found that the problems of future physics specialists in the ability to find unusual ideas as a result of training, developed imagination and intellectual reasoning, the ability to create unique texts and invent discoveries, the ability to search for unusual things and test new ideas, that is, the development of creativity of future physics specialists have not been considered [6-7]. And the presence of indicators of creativity among future physics specialists will help to find solutions to the difficulties that are currently faced in fulfilling the requirements of Industry 4.0 programs. Based on this, improving the training of future physics specialists in the context of STEM education based on the development of their creativity is becoming one of the most pressing problems of our time.

Purpose and objectives of the stud. To identify theoretical problems of teaching physics in the conditions of STEM education through the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical-psychological, methodological research, to develop a general structural (components and Indicators) model for the development of creativity of future physics specialists.

Research methods. In the course of the study, the selection of scientific papers was carried out through a systematic review based on well-defined criteria. The selection process for scientific articles was developed in accordance with the "PRISMA" declaration. In addition, the criteria for the search and grouping of literature were selected journal articles in English, Kazakh, Russian, the indication of the terms "STEM education", "STEM project", "physics teaching", "creativity" in the title, annotation or keywords, the presentation of methods for assessing creativity, the presentation of conclusions on the impact of STEM education on creativity. In addition, the study used qualitative research methods with narrative design, a control method of data collection.

Research results and Discussion. In the course of educational activities, it is necessary to create conditions for effective inclusion of self-taught persons in the creative process, because in cognitive activity, the creative potential of the individual develops. The difficulty here lies in the organization and regulation of the creative process, which forms a conscious understanding of the creative independence of the individual.

In pedagogy, creativity is explained by such abilities as ingenuity, imagination, intuition, problem solving. Here, the multi-facet of these abilities is mentioned. Creativity is the basis of creative educational activity, but it is not a noble ability. The definitions given in science for the concept of "creativity" can be seen in the table below.

Currently, the importance of teaching physics is the formation of a creative person who learns new opportunities of society, can apply the acquired physical knowledge in practice, and the role of a teacher is to create an environment in which another creative future physics teacher will be trained. At the same time, today's globalization is the formation of a comprehensively developed person who can freely interact in the labor market in any country in the world and meet the needs of the times.

American scientist E. Torrens, who was engaged in the study of creative abilities, proposed a model of creativity, which included the following three factors:

- mental agility;
- flexibility;
- the exception, the own.

In this case, the symbol of creativity is not the quality of the result, but the characteristics and processes that activate the productivity of creativity. Today, to describe creativity, the pedestals proposed by A. Stern, which are used today by many researchers, are used.

The study of creativity, in which a very strong interest has grown in recent years, considers in four main aspects:

- creative trend.
- creative product.
- creative personality.
- creative environment (Environment, structure, social context that forms the requirement for a creative product). These pedestals are often used together.

Improving our understanding of pedagogical and psychological conditions from scientific works, the system of developing the creativity of future physics specialists using STEM technologies, which we propose, includes the following pedagogical conditions:

- provide additional STEM-based topics to the physics teaching methodology;
- in order to develop the creativity of future physics specialists, organize their knowledge in STEM and independent work in such a way that it is understandable;
- to determine the interdisciplinarity between physical disciplines and STEM disciplines;
- flexibility in the use of content, methods, forms, means of teaching physical disciplines aimed at developing the creativity of future physics specialists through the use of STEM;

And in our opinion, creativity is the creative activity of a person, aimed at independently presenting problems, creating many new ideas and techniques for solving various pedagogical tasks and new types of knowledge.

At the same time, we determined the content of educational activities of future physics specialists with the definition of criteria for the development of creativity (figure 1).

Those included in their structure:

The peculiarity of thinking is the presence of a feature of thinking in the performance of a task;

the ability to independently perform a task, independence;

the ability to show individuality; the ability to produce a unique solution to a problem, Problem, task; the ability to use several unique elements in solving a new problem.

Figure 1 - General structural model for the development of creativity of future physics specialist

If we consider the works of domestic scientists who have studied the concept of "creativity" "K.M. Nagymzhanova:" creative thinking keeps the poles in balance and connects units that look opposite. When we observe students, what we discover is that they often give the answers we expect from them. They only say that they are completely confident. But all new creatives are not defined, a child in the status of "smart and resourceful" avoids being creative because he is afraid of losing his reputation. And such a situation leads to mechanical thinking. This creates stability, as well as boredom. Mechanical thinking is the greatest threat to creative thinking, that is, it eliminates the possibility of experiencing and discovering new things. The next threat may be preconceived criticism. Often an unusual, incorrect connection is the basis for creative thinking, and early criticism stifles new development". [12]

Ospanova B. A. in her concept, activity in the formation of creativity of future specialists serves as the basis for structuring the values and goals of the personality, its interpersonal, socio-psychological space. At the same time, it emphasizes the role of activity in creativity, adhering to the opinion that activity projects the actions, strategies and attitudes of the individual [13]

C. Berdibayeva emphasizes the role of aitys in the development of personality creativity. It is believed that through the art of aitys, one can develop human creativity [14].

As a result of the above scientific research, we came to the following conclusion: the most common concepts of creativity include: - identify creativity in relation to creative achievement. In it, creativity is the actions of a person that form new, unique values. - creativity is discussed as the original ability of a person to express himself.

Conclusions. The current state of STEM education in the training of future physics specialists abroad and in our own country was studied. In order to improve the efficiency of teaching physics, we Components DIMENSIONS AND INDICATIONS Levels - quickly performs a creative task; - ability to change the way you solve problems and problems suddenly; - ability to quickly recognize new; - ability to demonstrate speed in any type of business; - the ability to generate several thoughts that meet the rule of the task, a witty thought, etc Mental agility Flexibility of thinking Feature of thinking - desire for experience; - flexible to new problems; - tendency to solve problems; - flexibility to discuss; - ability to go to the limit of the task; - ability to find multiple ways to solve a problem, Problem; - ability to give several correct answers to a new problem, etc - availability of thinking skills in completing tasks; - ability to independently perform tasks, independence; - ability to show individuality; - solving a unique solution to a problem, Problem, task; - get multiple unique elements from hand to hand in solving a new problem; Low Middle High 86 will analyze the existing STEM resources, identify their features and recommend using them in the training of future physics specialists. The importance and significance of STEM education in teaching physics is determined. The effectiveness of using STEM educational resources in any form of teaching physics has been determined. The organization of the educational process in the context of STEM education ensures the continuation of pedagogical activity to a new qualitative level. At the same time, it is obvious that it contributes to the development of cognitive activities, creativity indicators, slightly increasing the didactic, informational, methodological and technological capabilities of the learning process.

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